

Disease management

Suitability of iodine test for detecting rice tungro virus (RTV) infection

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Sets of 20 20-d-old plants each of TN1, TKM9, and ADT31 rice varieties were inoculated by confining viruliferous green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* Distant at 2 insects/plant. Plants showing typical leaf discoloration and stunting, stunting alone, and no visible symptom were grouped separately, by variety (Table 1).

In iodine tests, most plants showing both leaf discoloration and stunting gave positive reactions (Table 2). No plants showing stunting alone reacted positively with the stain. In ADT31, one of three plants showing no visible symptoms of RTV infection reacted

Table 1. Rice plant response to RTV inoculation.

Variety	Leaf discoloration + stunting		Stunting		No symptoms	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
TN1	15	75	3	15	2	10
TKM9	13	65	4	20	3	15
ADT31	11	55	6	30	3	15
Total	39	—	13	—	8	—

Table 2. Reaction of tungro-inoculated rice plants in the iodine test.

Variety	Leaf discoloration + stunting			Stunting	No symptoms	
	Plants (no.)		Plants tested ^a (no.)		Plants (no.)	
	Tested	With positive reaction		%	Tested	With positive reaction
TN1	15	10	66.1	3	2	0
TKM9	13	11	84.6	3	4	0
ADT31	11	9	81.8	6	3	1
Total	39	30		12	9	1

^a None showed positive reaction.

positively.

These results suggest that interpretation of iodine test results

should be done cautiously, since 23% of plants showing typical tungro symptoms did not give positive reactions. □

Biological control of rice blast (BI) with antagonistic bacteria

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is found in most rice-growing areas of the world. It is common in irrigated and rainfed bunded rice culture, but is more serious in upland rice. Because of the instability of the BI fungus and the marked variability in its pathogenicity, which results in different races of the organism, control and management are difficult. Use of fungicides is limited by cost and development of host resistance has been only partially successful.

In developing alternate strategies for disease management, we screened strains of bacteria isolated from IRRI ricefields for their antagonism toward *P. oryzae*.

More than 100 bacterial strains were initially screened in the laboratory. Four

strains (2 fluorescent and 2 nonfluorescent) that caused maximum inhibition of *P. oryzae* were chosen for testing. The average diameter of the inhibition zones was 38.5 mm for strain 7-14 (fluorescent), 30.4 mm for strain 4-15 (fluorescent), 26.3 mm for strain 33, and 21.1 mm for strain 4-03. Using standard procedures, mutant strains were generated by incorporating resistance to rifampicin (R) or rifampicin and nalidixic acid (RN) (100 ppm). The mutant strains retained their ability to inhibit *P. oryzae* (see figure).

The field experiment in a randomized complete block design with four replications was conducted at the IRRI site for upland rice research for acid soils in Mahipon, Cavinti, the Philippines. Seeds of UPLRi-5 rice were coated with bacteria as follows.

Bacterial cells from 24 h grown cultures of test strains were scraped into a 1% carboxymethylcellulose buffer. Seeds (1.3 kg per treatment) were mixed

Inhibition of *Pyricularia oryzae* in PDA by fluorescent pseudomonad strain 7-14 and by its mutant 7-14 RN.

with the bacterial suspension and incubated overnight in polythene bags at 25 °C. Excess buffer-bacteria mixture was drained and seeds were dried in sterile air for 12 h before sowing in 4 × 5 m field plots.

At sowing, seeds had 10⁹ colony-forming units (CFU)/g. Seeds coated with fungarin (CGA 49104; 8 g/kg seed)